

Measuring Green Purchase Intention Through Green Product and Green Advertising: Mediated by Green Brand Image

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Abstract

The increasing consumption and waste of clothing contributes to environmental degradation that endangers lives. Consumers who are becoming more aware of environmental issues are shifting to sustainable clothing. However, despite having an awareness of the environment, there are still many consumers who have not taken concrete steps on this matter, especially the younger generation. This study aims to determine the effect of green product and green advertising on green purchase intention through green brand image as a mediating variable. This research is an explanatory type with data collection through questionnaires and data processing using SmartPLS 4.1.0.9 software, with a sample of 100 Eiger Semarang consumers. The results of this study state that green product and green advertising have an influence on green purchase intention, both directly and indirectly through green brand image. The green brand image variable as a mediating variable in this study partially influences the two independent variables.

Keywords: Green Product; Green Advertising; Green Brand Image; Green Purchase Intention

1. Introduction

Consumption activities are increasing in line with the growth of the human population. The culture of consumerism is caused by accelerated globalization, one of which is in the realm of fashion which in this category can change fashion or trends very quickly, and contributes a large amount of waste. The Sustainable Fashion Forum revealed that global clothing consumption is expected to increase from 62 million tons in 2023 to 102 million tons in 2030, an estimated increase of 63%. As a result, global textile waste is expected to reach 300 million tons by 2050 [10]. Fashion products generate a carbon footprint from the start of yarn to waste. The average manufacturing process of 1 kg of fabric will produce 20-23 kg of greenhouse gases which indirectly contribute to 4-8% of the total global greenhouse gases or in the range of 1.7 - 2.1 billion tons of CO₂-e/year. This will make the fashion industry the cause of increasing carbon content in the earth's atmosphere with 25% by 2050 [30]. Fashion waste that is increasingly piling up raises concerns because not all of it can be recycled and the impact is very bad for the environment.

The impact of fast fashion consumerism that is very damaging to the environment has made consumers begin to realize that consuming and using environmentally friendly fashion products is necessary. This is also the case in Indonesian society, through The Nielsen Global Survey of Corporate Social Responsibility in 2023, 68% of Indonesian consumers are likely to choose products from companies that have a clear commitment to sustainability and measurability through ESG. McKinsey also found that 40% of Gen Z and millennial consumers will consider the environmental impact of a product before they buy it [23]. Through a survey Standard Insights [24] contained in Consumer Report Indonesia 2024, it is known that 80% of Indonesian consumers have concerns about environmental issues, where Tangerang, Surabaya, Semarang, and Bogor are cities with high levels of environmental awareness. On the other hand, through the same survey, it is stated that the older generation shows the highest environmental concern. This is supported by a survey

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conducted by PwC, which states that 86% of global consumers have begun to switch to environmentally friendly products, but there are still many younger generations who have not become eco-friendly consumers [21]. This situation indicates that there are still opportunities for fashion companies to innovate into sustainable products. For companies, this can be both a problem and an opportunity to increase the younger generations interest in environmentally friendly products so that they can maximize existing market opportunities and result in increased sales and profits

Figure 1 Eiger Green Search Trends

Eiger Adventure (EIGER) is a fashion brand that provides environmentally friendly fashion products through the Eiger Green movement which began in 2021. Eiger Green, which is relatively new, still gets little attention from the public, especially from Eiger consumers themselves. For this reason, Eiger needs to provide consistent education and promotion because consumer motivation to buy environmentally friendly products is formed from price factors, product quality, product information, ease of access, and brand image [9]. That way Eiger must put more effort into providing and introducing their green products to consumers through green advertising and building a green brand image so that consumers trust more so that interest in buying Eiger Green will grow.

Thus, this study aims to examine the relationship between green product and green advertising on green purchase intention on environmentally friendly fashion products, namely Eiger Green in Semarang. Furthermore, see the mediating role of green brand image between the relationship between green product and green advertising on green purchase intention.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Green Product

Green products are products made from environmentally friendly raw materials that are not harmful to health and have packaging with an eco-label [15]. The indicators for measuring green products are:

- Product packaging
- Eco-label on packaging
- Product raw materials
- Product safety

2.2. Green Advertising

Green advertising is a tool used in delivering environmentally friendly messages and positioning them in the minds of consumers [8]. The indicators used in measuring green advertising are:

- Show a caring attitude towards the environment

- Environmentally friendly concept
- Increase knowledge related to environmentally friendly products

2.3. Green Brand Image

Green brand image is a series of consumer perceptions of a brand that is closely related to commitment to the environment [8]. The indicators used in measuring green brand image are:

- Environmental professional
- Environmental reputation
- Environmental successful
- Environmental concern
- Environmental trustworthy

2.4. Green Purchase Intention

Green purchase intention is consumer interest in buying environmentally friendly products [27]. The indicators used in measuring green purchase intention include:

- Interested in consuming products from brands that care about the environment because of their concern for the environment
- Hope to consume environmentally friendly products in the future
- Overall consuming environmentally friendly products is a matter of pride

2.5. Research Method

This study uses an explanatory quantitative approach, employing non-probability sampling through purposive techniques to select respondents who meet the research characteristics [25]. The population in this study consisted of young Eiger consumers aged 17–35 years old in Semarang City, with 100 valid responses collected. To measure the constructs in this study, a Likert scale of 1-4 was used with data collection through a questionnaire objective [6]. In preparing this questionnaire, indicators from existing research were used to obtain values on the variables of green product, green advertising, green brand image, and green purchase intention. This study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) which is processed by the Partial Least Square (PLS) method using SmartPLS software.

Figure 2 Conceptual Frame Work

2.6. Hypothesis

2.6.1. The Effect of Green Product on Green Purchase Intention

Green products have a positive and significant influence on green purchase intention, this is because people are starting to have high attention to environmental issues, so that with a better green product, green purchase intention is also increasing [14].

H1: Green product has a positive and significant influence on green purchase intention

2.6.2. The Effect of Green Product on Green Brand Image

Green products have a positive and significant influence on brand image. A brand's green brand image will be more trusted by consumers when the brand can provide green products with benefits that meet consumer's needs [5]. Before that, the beginning of a green brand image can be embedded in a brand not only with the company's claim that they are an environmentally friendly brand, the green brand image will be more trusted by consumers when the brand can produce or have a green product [7].

H2: Green product has a positive and significant influence on green brand image

2.6.3. The Effect of Green Advertising on Green Purchase Intention

Research shows that there is a positive and significant influence between green advertising and green purchase intention. Green advertising is used to provide information related to environmentally friendly products and services to consumers. The messages contained in advertisements, writing styles, and designs provide information that can increase consumer sensitivity to the environment so that they switch to using environmentally friendly products [2,15,20].

H3: Green advertising has a positive and significant influence on green purchase intention

2.6.4. The Effect of Green Advertising on Green Brand Image

The information and impressions provided through green advertising greatly influence the formation of a green brand image in the minds of consumers. Previous research said that green advertising has a positive and significant influence on green brand image. For a company, green advertising is a tool used to convey environmentally friendly messages and position their green products in the minds of consumers [7,8].

H4: Green advertising has a positive and significant influence on green brand image

2.6.5. The Effect of Green Brand Image on Green Purchase Intention

Previous research shows a positive and significant effect of green brand image on green purchase intention. Consumer emotions and thoughts that arise because of the green brand image of the importance of environmental care encourage consumers to get involved and contribute as an act of concern for the environment which leads to an increase in green purchase intention [1,8]. This shows that consumers see the brand image before interest arises.

H5: Green brand image has a positive and significant influence on green purchase intention

2.6.6. The Mediating Role of Green Brand Image

The rising trend of environmentally friendly products among consumers has led to competitive competition between companies providing green products. Producing green products in accordance with market demand will maintain a competitive advantage and improve the company's green brand image, with a better image, consumers' green purchase intention will increase and create new market development [2]. Previous research shows the results that green brand image has a positive and significant effect in mediating the relationship between green products and purchase intention [7,17].

Green brand image is not only related to the products accessed by customers, but also the company's behavior towards the environment [26] where it is formed through a series of perceptions obtained, one of which is through green advertising, so that green advertising can form a green brand image in the minds of consumers [19]. According to the previous research, green brand image has a positive and significant influence in mediating the relationship between green advertising and purchase intention [7,17,19]. Consumers will buy environmentally friendly products when consumers have an interest in a product and see a positive image of the company towards the environment [18].

H6: Green brand image can mediate the relationship between green product and green purchase intention.

H7: Green brand image can mediate the relationship between green advertising and green purchase intention.

3. Result

3.1. Measurement Model Assessment Result

Measurement model is used to measure the relationship between indicators and their construct, this is done by testing validity and reliability. The validity test consists of testing convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity test results with a loading factor value of > 0.70 are said to be ideal, but in empirical research the value of > 0.50 is still acceptable [13]. In addition, it must have an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.50 [11]. It can be seen in Table 2. that all items in the construct have loading factor values ranging between 0.734 and 0.936. All constructs have an AVE value > 0.50 so that all constructs can be said to be convergently valid.

Table 1 Convergent Validity Measurement

Constructs	λ	AVE	Description
Green Product		0.639	Valid
Eiger Green packaging is environmentally friendly packaging	0.783		Valid
Eiger Green logo on each package is easily recognizable	0.790		Valid
Eiger Green products are made from non-toxic natural raw materials	0.815		Valid
Eiger Green products are recyclable	0.783		Valid
Eiger Green products are biodegradable	0.734		Valid
Eiger Green products are harmless and do not pollute the environment	0.883		Valid
Green Advertising		0.701	Valid
I like Eiger's advertising because it conveys a message of environmentalism	0.893		Valid
The benefits of Eiger's environmentally friendly activities are well conveyed	0.742		Valid
Eiger's advertising concept with an environmentally friendly theme makes me more interested.	0.844		Valid
Eiger's advertising has increased my knowledge about environmentally friendly themes.	0.813		Valid
Eiger's advertising provides complete information about Eiger Green products.	0.884		Valid
Constructs	λ	AVE	Description
Green Brand Image		0.605	Valid
Eiger has a professional reputation for environmental stewardship	0.780		Valid
Eiger is a brand committed to the environment	0.789		Valid
Eiger is a brand that is successful in its environmental performance	0.752		Valid
Eiger is a brand known for its concern for the environment	0.747		Valid
Eiger is a brand that can fulfill its commitment to protecting the environment	0.817		Valid
Green Purchase Intention		0.761	Valid
I am interested in buying Eiger Green products	0.936		Valid
I am interested in buying Eiger Green products because it has a "for Earth, for Later" program.	0.846		Valid
I will buy Eiger Green products in the future	0.852		Valid
Eiger Green products are my top choice	0.826		Valid
I am proud to be an Eiger Green user as an environmentally friendly product.	0.898		Valid

Note. λ = standardized factor loadings, AVE = average variance extracted

Table 2 Discriminant Validity Cross-loading

Variable	Indicator	Green Advertising	Green Image	Brand	Green Product	Green Intention	Purchase	
Green Product	GP1	0.525	0.597		0.783	0.560		
	GP2	0.394	0.638		0.790	0.473		
	GP3	0.548	0.651		0.815	0.566		
	GP4	0.397	0.558		0.783	0.525		
	GP5	0.444	0.475		0.734	0.455		
	GP6	0.531	0.738		0.883	0.562		
Green Advertising	GA1	0.893	0.664		0.495	0.537		
	GA2	0.742	0.574		0.463	0.532		
	GA3	0.844	0.666		0.518	0.562		
	GA4	0.813	0.596		0.520	0.545		
	GA5	0.884	0.638		0.490	0.554		
Green Intention	Purchase	GPI1	0.562	0.615		0.629	0.936	
		GPI2	0.594	0.628		0.596	0.846	
		GPI3	0.583	0.634		0.565	0.852	
		GPI4	0.593	0.603		0.495	0.826	
		GPI5	0.512	0.637		0.575	0.898	
Variable	Indicator	Green Advertising	Green Image	Brand	Green Product	Green Intention	Purchase	
Green Brand Image	GBI1	0.597	0.780		0.493	0.492		
	GBI2	0.545	0.789		0.791	0.593		
	GBI3	0.576	0.752		0.515	0.560		
	GBI4	0.621	0.747		0.581	0.600		
	GBI5	0.584	0.817		0.574	0.520		

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Table 3 Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Variables	Green Advertising	Green Image	Brand	Green Product	Green Intention	Purchase
Green Advertising	0.837					
Green Brand Image	0.752	0.778				
Green Product	0.595	0.770		0.799		
Green Intention	0.653	0.715		0.657	0.872	

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Table 4 Construct Reliability

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	rho_A	Composite reliability
Green Advertising	0.892	0.894	0.921
Green Brand Image	0.836	0.838	0.884
Green Product	0.886	0.893	0.914
Green Purchase Intention	0.921	0.922	0.941

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Discriminant validity is assessed through cross-loading and Fornell-Larcker Criterion, where in order to be said to be valid, the correlation value of the construct with the construct itself must be greater than the correlation value with other constructs [22]. The cross-loading value in Table 2. shows that the cross-loading value of each indicator on its own construct is greater than the cross-loading value with other constructs. For example, item GP1 with green product has a value of 0.783 which is the highest value when compared to the value of GP1 with other variables. The results of the Fornell-Larcker Criterion in Table 3. show that the green product, green advertising, green brand image, and green purchase intention variables are valid because they have met the criteria that the construct value with the construct itself is greater than the construct value with other constructs. That way all constructs can be said to be discriminantly valid.

Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability both have a rule of thumb > 0.70 . Table 4. shows that all constructs in the study have a value of > 0.70 , so all constructs in this study were found to be reliable because they were in accordance with the rule of thumbs [11].

3.2. Structural Model Assessment Results

Structural model assessment is carried out to describe the relationship between latent variables. This assessment is done with the R-square, Q-square, and Goodness-of-Fit (GoF) tests. The expected R-square value is between 0 and 1 [22]. The criteria for the R-square value is said to be strong if the value is close to 0.65, moderate if close to 0.33, weak if close to 0.19.

Table 5 R-square and communality

Factor	R-square	Communality
Green Brand Image	0.726	0.375
Green Purchase Intention	0.568	0.606
Average	0.647	0.490

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

The green brand image variable is included in the strong category because it exceeds the value of 0.65, as well as the green purchase intention variable is included in the strong category because the value is close to 0.65 [22]. The R-square value of the green brand image variable is 0.726, which means that the green product and green advertising variables can predict the green brand image variable by 72.6%. The R-square value of the green purchase intention variable is 0.568, which means that the green product and green advertising variables can predict the green purchase intention variable by 56.8%.

In the Q-square assessment when the Q2 value is greater than 0, means that the model has good predictive relevance, and vice versa [28]. The following is the calculation of Q-square:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R1^2) (1 - R2^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.726^2) (1 - 0.568^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.527) (1 - 0.322)$$

$$Q^2 = 0.679$$

Based on the results of the Q2 calculation above, the Q2 value is 0.679, this means that this research model has good predictive relevance. The value of 0.679 also indicates that 67.9% of the variation in this research data can be explained by the research model, while the other 32.1% is explained by other factors outside this research model.

The Goodness-of-fit (GoF) index is an index that measures the predictive performance of the measurement model. Specifically, it can be understood as the geometric mean of the average communality and average R2 of the endogenous latent variables [29]. The communality value is obtained from the blindfolding process in Smart-PLS (cross-validated communality) which can be seen in Table 6. Goodness-of-Fit (GoF) assessment must have a GoF index ranging from 0 to 1 with values of 0.1 (low), 0.25 (medium), and 0.36 (high) [12].

$$\sqrt{(\text{Communality} \times R^2)}$$

$$= \sqrt{(0.490 \times 0.647)}$$

$$= \sqrt{0.317}$$

$$= 0.563$$

The GoF calculation above shows a result of 0.563 which is included in the high category. This means that the measurement model has a high level of fit.

3.3. Hypothesis Testing Results

The hypothesis in this study is formed through the existence of a direct relationship (direct effect) and an indirect relationship (indirect effect) between the variables. In this study, the path coefficient value obtained through the bootstrapping method is used as a tool to test hypotheses both through direct effects and indirect effects. The t-statistic value > t-table 1.96 and the p-value <0.05 or 5% significance indicate that the exogenous variables have a positive and significant influence on the endogenous variables tested, it can also be said that the hypothesis is accepted [28].

Table 6 Hypothesis Testing Results

No.	Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	t-statistics	p-values	Results
H1	Green product-> Green purchase intention	0.251	2.212	0.027	Supported
H2	Green product-> Green brand image	0.499	7.137	0.000	Supported
H3	Green advertising -> Green purchase intention	0.255	3.004	0.003	Supported
H4	Green advertising > Green brand image	0.455	5.674	0.000	Supported
H5	Green brand image -> Green purchase intention	0.330	2.819	0.005	Supported
Indirect Hypothesis					
H6	Green advertising > Green brand image-> Green purchase intention	0.150	2.336	0.020	Supported
H7	Green product-> Green brand image-> Green purchase intention	0.165	2.795	0.005	Supported

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

The direct effect test results in Table 6. show that all tested hypotheses, namely Hypothesis 1, Hypothesis 2, Hypothesis 3, Hypothesis 4, Hypothesis 5 have a P-value <0.05 and a t-statistic value >1.96, this indicates a positive and significant influence between the tested variables. The test results above also show that the effect of green product on green brand image has the highest significance as indicated by the highest t-statistic value of 7.137, while the effect of green product on green purchase intention has the lowest significance with a t-statistic value of 2.212.

The indirect effect test results in Table 6. show that the tested hypothesis meets the rule of thumb, which has a t-statistic value >1.96 and a p-value <0.05 . This means that the mediating role of the green brand image variable has a positive and significant effect. As a result, Hypothesis 6 and Hypothesis 7 are accepted. The most significant mediating effect occurs in the relationship between green product and green purchase intention mediated by green brand image because it has the highest t-statistic value of 2.795.

Mediation that occurs in this study is partial mediation. Partial mediation occurs when the results of all tests, both direct and indirect have significant results with a p-value <0.05 . This means that the green brand image variable can mediate the relationship between green product and green advertising on green purchase intention. However, if the green brand image variable is removed, the green product and green advertising variables will still be able to influence green purchase intention. So Eiger's focus in this case must be greater on green products and green advertising for Eiger Green.

4. Discussion

The results of this study indicate that there is a positive and significant relationship in the first hypothesis, namely between green product and green purchase intention. This is indicated by the t-statistic value of 2.212 and a p-value of 0.027 in the direct effect test, this means that Hypothesis 1 is accepted. The results of the study are supported by previous research which also states that there is a positive and significant relationship between green product and green purchase intention [14,16]. Consumers think that Eiger Green has met the criteria as an environmentally friendly product because the raw materials contain environmentally friendly materials and some are even made from recycled bottles so that they are not harmful to the environment and consumers themselves. In addition, Eiger Green also has its own logo to show that its products are environmentally friendly products, and consumers also stated that the logo is easily recognizable. Eiger Green also uses environmentally friendly packaging for its products. The better a green product is, the more consumer buying interest in environmentally friendly products will increase.

The results of testing the second hypothesis (H2) regarding the effect of green products on green brand image provide positive and significant results, this is indicated by a t-statistic value of 7.137 and a p-value of 0.000 in the direct effect test, this means that Hypothesis 2 is accepted. The results of this study are supported by previous research which also states that there is a positive and significant influence between green product and green brand image [5,7]. Consumers think that Eiger Green has met the criteria for being an environmentally friendly product. Eiger Green with good product quality and specifications can generate consumer interest in buying Eiger Green products, because consumer buying interest in green products tends to arise because consumers believe and feel that the product is ecologically beneficial. A good green product will also create trust and good perceptions of the company, in other words, a good green product will create a good green brand image too.

The results of testing the third hypothesis (H3) regarding the effect of green advertising on green purchase intention provide positive and significant results, this is indicated by a t-statistic value of 3.004 and a p-value of 0.003 in the direct effect test, this means that Hypothesis 3 is accepted. These results are in line with previous research which states that green advertising has a positive influence on green purchase intention [8]. Consumer awareness of the environment supported by information will increase their knowledge about the concept of environmental love, this knowledge will encourage consumers to behave to love the environment, one of which is using environmentally friendly products.

The results of testing the fourth hypothesis (H4) regarding the effect of green advertising on green brand image provide positive and significant results, this is indicated by a t-statistic value of 5.674 and a p-value of 0.000 in the direct effect test, this means that Hypothesis 4 is accepted. The results of this study are supported by previous research which states that there is a positive and significant influence between green advertising on green brand image [7]. Information about green products or companies is contained in green advertising. Green brand image is formed through consumer perceptions of a product or company, while perceptions can arise through experience or information obtained, so green advertising is very important for the creation of a good Eiger green brand image in consumers.

The results of testing the fifth hypothesis (H5) regarding the effect of green brand image on green purchase intention provide positive and significant results, this is indicated by a t-statistic value of 2.819 and a p-value of 0.005 in the direct effect test, this means that Hypothesis 5 is accepted. The results of this study are supported by previous research which states that there is a positive and significant influence between green brand image and green purchase intention [1,8]. Consumers have long seen Eiger as a brand related to nature, the existence of this sustainability commitment makes Eiger's image more trusted by consumers as a brand that is friendly to the environment, this trust is what creates green purchase intention in Eiger consumers.

The results of testing the sixth hypothesis (H6) regarding the effect of green products on green purchase intention through green brand image provide positive and significant results, this is indicated by a t-statistic value of 2.795 and a p-value of 0.005 in the specific test of indirect effect, this means that Hypothesis 6 is accepted. The results of this study indicate a partial mediation effect. This means that whether or not the green brand image variable is mediated, the green product variable will still have an effect on green purchase intention. The results of this study are supported by previous research which states that green products have a positive and significant effect on green brand image [7]. Furthermore, this research is also supported by previous research which states that green brand image has a positive and significant influence on green purchase intention [8]. Eiger Green products have been deemed good by consumers because their features as environmentally friendly products have met the standards.

The results of testing the seventh hypothesis (H7) regarding the effect of green advertising on green purchase intention through green brand image provide positive and significant results, this is indicated by a t-statistic value of 2.336 and a p-value of 0.020 in the specific indirect effect test, this means that Hypothesis 7 is accepted. This means that whether or not the green brand image variable is mediated, the green advertising variable will still have an effect on green purchase intention. These results are supported by previous research which states that green advertising has a positive influence on green purchase intention [8]. It is also supported by previous research [7] which states that green advertising has a positive and significant effect on green brand image. Furthermore, this research is also supported by previous research [1], which states that green brand image has a positive and significant influence on green purchase intention. The main purpose of green advertising is to provide information so as to attract consumers to buy environmentally friendly products. The existence of green advertising will increase the company's green brand. Eiger's green advertising can generate consumer interest in buying Eiger Green products, supported by the existence of a green brand image, Eiger Green has more opportunities to be chosen by consumers when buying environmentally friendly fashion products.

5. Conclusion

This study concludes that Eiger Green's good and appropriate green product and green advertising performance can influence green purchase intention in its consumers. Besides that, in this case, green brand image has a significant role in mediating this influence.

There are three important things that can be suggested from the results of this study. First, researchers suggest that Eiger can add a description of product specifications not only on the online store page but also on the packaging or hangtag, so that consumers can read again related to product specifications when they already have Eiger Green products. Eiger can also provide knowledge directly to consumers through store employees when consumers buy Eiger Green at offline stores. Second, Eiger can create a separate section or category for Eiger Green on all online pages such as the web, Eiger Apps, Instagram, YouTube, Shopee, and other marketplaces, and be more consistent in holding events and creating content about sustainability, so that consumer knowledge continues to be updated and increased. Third, Eiger must be more active in branding sustainability through green advertising and seeking certification as an environmentally friendly product, so that Eiger's green brand image is more evident in the minds of consumers.

Limitation

The results of this study are limited to Eiger consumers in Semarang City, which does not fully represent consumer behavior in other regions. Future research can concentrate on other regions or other similar industries, so that the findings can generalize the findings in this study. This research only focuses on factors originating from the company, for this reason, future research can concentrate on other factors originating from consumers such as environmental knowledge, environmental awareness, and green perceived value in order to see other influences on green purchase intention.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

The authors report that there are no conflicts of interest in this study.

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